

INFLUENCE OF SEMI-CRYSTALLINE MICROSTRUCTURE ON HYDROGEN PERMEABILITY OF POLY(ETHER-KETONE-KETONE)

HYPOCCRYT Project

HYdrogen Permeability of Organic Composites at CRYogenic Temperature

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LH2 storage for aerospace applications

H₂ gas storage (P = 350 → 700 bar)
 $\rho = 25\text{-}35 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$

Hydrogen Storage for Mobility: A Review - Etienne Rivard

TPRD - Thermally Activated Pressure Relief Device

Credit: Process Modeling Group, Nuclear Engineering Division, Argonne National Laboratory (ANL)

Liquid H₂ storage (T = 20 K)
 $\rho = 65\text{-}70 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$

www.Linde.com

LH2 storage : leakage control

$P = 1-4 \text{ bar}$
 $T = -253 \text{ °C}$

Permeability P
($\text{mol.m.m}^{-2}\text{MPa}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$)

Diffusion D
($\text{m}^2.\text{s}^{-1}$)

Solubility S
($\text{mol.MPa}^{-1}\text{m}^{-3}$)

[1] : Klopffer et al. – Rev. IFP, Vol. 56 - 2001

Permeability theory

Influencing parameters

- Density
- Polymer State

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Permeability theory

Influencing parameters

Density

Polymer State

Crystallinity

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($mol.m.m^{-2}MPa^{-1}s^{-1}$)

Diffusion D
($m^2.s^{-1}$)

Solubility S
($mol.MPa^{-1}m^{-3}$)

Crystallite

[2] : Monson et al. – J. APPL. POLYM. SCI. - 2013

Permeability theory

Influencing parameters

- Density
- Polymer State
- Crystallinity
- Carbon Content

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($mol.m.m^{-2}MPa^{-1}s^{-1}$)

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($mol.MPa^{-1}m^{-3}$)

Permeability theory

Influencing parameters

- Density
- Polymer State
- Crystallinity
- Carbon Content
- Gas size
- And more

Carbon filler

Crystallite

Permeability P
($mol.m.m^{-2}MPa^{-1}s^{-1}$)

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Solubility S
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Permeability theory

Influencing parameters

Carbon Content

Density

Crystallinity

Polymer State

Gas size

How the semi-crystalline microstructure of thermoplastic polymers influences its permeability ?

PEKK grades for investigating the effect of crystallinity

PEKK	6002		7002		8002	
	AR	CC	AR	CC	AR	CC
Xc (%)	1.1	22	1.2	28	6.2	33

* AR = As Received ; CC = Cold Crystallized

Crystallinity of the as received (AR) PEKK 6002, 7002 and 8002 films and cold crystallized (CC) films determined from DSC results at 10°C/min

PEKK	6002	7002	8002
Monomer	-----C ₂₀ H ₁₂ O ₃ -----		
T_g (°C)	160	162	165
T_m (°C)	305	332	358
T/I Ratio	60/40	70/30	80/20

[3]

Monomers of the T and I forms

[3] : T. Choupin – PhD ParisTech - 2017

➤ Permeability Apparatus

$$p_{He,acc}(i) = p_{He,acc}(i - 1) + p_{He}(i)$$

Helium permeability, diffusion and solubility results of PEKK for 0,5 bar of differential pressure at 293K

PEKK	6002 ●		7002 ■		8002 ▼	
	AR	CC	AR	CC	AR	CC
Permeability (mol/m/s/MPa) × 10 ⁹	1.93	0.995	1.87	0.968	1.71	1.00
Diffusion (m ² /s) × 10 ¹⁰	1.69	1.20	1.66	1.26	1.55	1.34
Solubility (mol/m ³ /MPa)	11.4	8.28	11.3	7.67	11.0	7.46

Can we consider all materials identical in terms of permeability ?
 → Is there a crystallinity threshold above which permeability remains constant ?

[2]

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→ Is there a crystallinity threshold above which permeability remains constant ?

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[4] : J. Crank – “The mathematics of diffusion” - 1975

Can we consider all materials identical in terms of permeability ?

→ ~~Is there a crystallinity threshold above which permeability remains constant ?~~

Permeability as a function of T/I ratio

Which model can explain the influence of the T/I ratio on permeability ?

Permeability vs. Crystallinity

Two-Phase Model (2PM)

	6002		7002		8002	
PEKK	AR	CC	AR	CC	AR	CC
X_c (%)	1.10	22.0	1.20	28.0	6.20	33.0

* AR = As Received ; CC = Cold Crystallized

« Two-Phase Model (2PM) » [1]

$$P_{SC} = (1 - X_c)D_a \times (1 - X_c)S_a$$

$$P_{SC} = (1 - X_c)^2 P_a$$

SC = Semi-Crystalline
A = Amorphous

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The 2-phase Model provides a rough prediction without describing the effect of the T/l ratio on the change in permeability.

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$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} X_c = \frac{\Delta h_m - \Delta h_{cf}}{\Delta h_{100\%}} \\ X_A = \frac{\Delta C_p(T_g)}{\Delta C_{p,0\%}(T_g)} \\ X_A = 1 - X_c \end{array} \right.$$

Permeability vs. Crystallinity

Refining the Two-Phase Model (2PM)

PEKK	6002		7002		8002	
	AR	CC	AR	CC	AR	CC
X_c (%)	1.10	22.0	1.20	28.0	6.20	33.0

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$$[6] \begin{cases} X_c = \frac{\Delta h_m - \Delta h_{cf}}{\Delta h_{100\%}} \rightarrow 130 \text{ J.g}^{-1} [5] \\ X_A = \frac{\Delta C_p(T_g)}{\Delta C_{p,0\%}(T_g)} \rightarrow 0.27 \text{ J.K}^{-1}.\text{g}^{-1} (\text{PEEK} [7]) \\ X_A = 1 - X_c \end{cases}$$

Linearity considering a 2-phase model

PEKK	6002		7002		8002	
	AR	CC	AR	CC	AR	CC
X_c (%)	1.10	22.0	1.20	28.0	6.20	33.0

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$$[6] \left\{ \begin{aligned} X_c &= \frac{\Delta h_m - \Delta h_{cf}}{\Delta h_{100\%}} \rightarrow 130 \text{ J.g}^{-1} [5] \\ X_{MAF} &= \frac{\Delta C_p(T_g)}{\Delta C_{p,0\%}(T_g)} \rightarrow 0.27 \text{ J.K}^{-1}.\text{g}^{-1} (\text{PEEK } [7]) \\ X_{RAF} &= 1 - X_{MAF} - X_c \end{aligned} \right.$$

« Three-Phases Model (3PM) » [6]

$$D_{SC} = X_{MAF}D_{MAF} + X_{RAF}D_{RAF}$$

$$S_{SC} = X_{MAF}S_{MAF} + X_{RAF}S_{RAF}$$

$$P_{SC} = D_{SC} \times S_{SC}$$

[5] : Blundell et al. – Polymer, Vol. 24 - 1983

[6] : Sonchaeng et al. - Prog. Polym. Sci. Vol. 86 – 2018

[7] : B. Wunderlich - Pure Appl. Chem.. vol. 67 -1995

Permeability vs. Crystallinity

Three-Phase Model (3PM)

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[6]
$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} X_c &= \frac{\Delta h_m - \Delta h_{cf}}{\Delta h_{100\%}} \\ X_{MAF} &= \frac{\Delta C_p(T_g)}{\Delta C_{p,0\%}(T_g)} \rightarrow 0.384 \text{ J.K}^{-1}.\text{g}^{-1} (\neq \text{PEEK [7]}) \\ X_{RAF} &= 1 - X_{MAF} - X_c \end{aligned} \right.$$

dH_m = f(dC_p) identical for all 3 grades

Same thermal behavior but different permeation behavior

PEKK	6002		7002		8002	
	AR	CC	AR	CC	AR	CC
Xc (%)	1.10	22.0	1.20	28.0	6.20	33.0
MAF(%)	90.3	47.0	84.6	40.0	75.4	30.0
RAF(%)	8.60	31.0	14.2	32.0	18.4	37.0

* AR = As Received ; CC = Cold Crystallized

« Three-Phase Model (3PM) » [6]

$$D_{SC} = X_{MAF}D_{MAF} + X_{RAF}D_{RAF}$$

$$S_{SC} = X_{MAF}S_{MAF} + X_{RAF}S_{RAF}$$

$$P_{SC} = D_{SC} \times S_{SC}$$

PEKK	6002		7002		8002	
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RAF(%)	8.60	31.0	14.2	32.0	18.4	37.0

* AR = As Received ; CC = Cold Crystallized

Possible explanations given in literature

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{RAF} < \rho_{MAF} \\ \rho_{RAF} > \rho_{MAF} \end{cases} ?$$

[6]

or

$$FV_{RAF} > FV_{MAF}$$

Evolution of the diffusion in the MAF and RAF of the different PEKK

Evolution of the solubility in the MAF and RAF of the different PEKK

Conclusions

The **crystallinity** is effectively a **key factor** of gas permeability

Increasing PEKK crystallinity does not always decrease gas permeability

RAF appears to become increasingly diffusible as the T/I ratio increases.

Perspectives

Permeability measurements of **CF/PEKK X002 Composites** are planned

The same samples will be tested in **cryogenic conditions** (down to **55K**)

Helium permeability curve as a function of the crystallinity of different PEKK

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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- [1] : M. H. Klopffer et B. Flaconneche. « Transport Properties of Gases in Polymers: Bibliographic Review ». Oil Gas Sci. Technol.. vol. 56. n° 3. p. 223-244. mai 2001. doi: 10.2516/ogst:2001021.
- [2] : L. Monson, S. I. Moon, et C. W. Extrand, « Permeation resistance of poly(ether ether ketone) to hydrogen, nitrogen, and oxygen gases », J. Appl. Polym. Sci., vol. 127, no 3, p. 1637-1642, févr. 2013, doi: 10.1002/app.37517.
- [3] : T. Choupin. « Mechanical performances of PEKK thermoplastic composites linked to their processing parameters »
- [4] : J. Crank, The mathematics of diffusion, 2d ed. Oxford, [Eng]: Clarendon Press, 1975
- [5] : D. J. Blundell et B. N. Osborn. « The morphology of poly(aryl-ether-ether-ketone) ». Polymer. vol. 24. n° 8. p. 953-958. août 1983. doi: 10.1016/0032-3861(83)90144-1.
- [6] : U. Sonchaeng. F. Iñiguez-Franco. R. Auras. S. Selke. M. Rubino. et L.-T. Lim. « Poly(lactic acid) mass transfer properties ». Prog. Polym. Sci.. vol. 86. p. 85-121. nov. 2018. doi: 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2018.06.008
- [7] : B. Wunderlich. « The ATHAS database on heat capacities of polymers ». Pure Appl. Chem.. vol. 67. no 6. p. 1019-1026. janv. 1995. doi: 10.1351/pac199567061019.